

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON DIGITAL EDUCATION
AND SOCIAL SCIENCE (2022) ICDESS 2022

STUDENTS' MISTAKES IN ARITHMETIC OPERATIONS: HOW DO STUDENTS REASON?

Benny N. Trisna, Muhammad Royani, Hajjah Rafiah, Syintia Septiani, Trie Widyastuti Maghfiroh

BACKGROUND

- There are still many students, especially elementary school students, who make mistakes in arithmetic operations of integers.
- To help students correct these mistakes, it is important for teachers to know, not only the causes, but also how students reason during the arithmetic operations.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- Describe the reasoning of students who make mistakes.
- Find the cause of students' mistakes in arithmetic operations.

METHOD

- This is a qualitative research
- Five 4th grade elementary school students who made mistakes in an arithmetic operation test were interviewed to find out their reasoning process and the reasons for their mistakes.

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON DIGITAL EDUCATION
AND SOCIAL SCIENCE (2022) ICDESS 2022

FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Addition

$$\begin{array}{r} 86 \\ 47 + \\ \hline 1213 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 765 \\ 58 + \\ \hline 71113 \end{array}$$

HOW?

- $6 + 7 = 13$
- $8 + 4 = 12$
- incorrect placement of the ones, tens, and hundreds digits

WHY?

- Subject do not understand place value in numbers

SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

86

47 +

13

12 +

133

Subtraction

$$\begin{array}{r} 96 \\ - 39 \\ \hline 60 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 3.4 \\ - 1.6 \\ \hline 2.2 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 96 \\ - 39 \\ \hline 67 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 970 \\ - 89 \\ \hline 100 \end{array}$$

HOW?

- **[top pictures]**: a number cannot be subtracted by a larger number
 - so the result is 0
 - so the large number must be subtracted by the small number
- **[bottom pictures]**: the subject applies the borrow rule 1 to the left number, but does not reduce the left number by 1
- incorrect placement of the ones and tens digits

WHY?

- the subject doesn't understand the meaning of units, tens, etc
- 1 ten = 10 ones,
 $34 = 3 \text{ tens} + 4 \text{ ones}$
 $= 2 \text{ tens} + 10 \text{ ones} + 4 \text{ ones}$
 $= 2 \text{ tens} + 14 \text{ ones}$

SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

$$96 = 8 \text{ tens} + 16 \text{ ones}$$

$$39 = 3 \text{ tens} + 9 \text{ ones} -$$

$$57 = 5 \text{ tens} + 7 \text{ ones}$$

Multiplication

$$\begin{array}{r} 16 \\ 12 \times \\ \hline 172 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 26 \\ 13 \times \\ \hline 78 \\ 26 \\ \hline 104 \end{array}$$

HOW?

- **[top picture]**: $6 \times 2 = 12$, write 2 save 1, $1 \times 6 = 6$, add 1 equals 7, $1 \times 1 = 1$
- **[bottom picture]**: $3 \times 6 = 18$, write 8 save 1, $3 \times 2 = 6$, add 1 equals 7; $1 \times 6 = 6$, $1 \times 2 = 2$; then $78 + 26 = 104$.

WHY?

- **[top picture]**: this is an incomplete multiplication steps; the subject knows the technique of saving in multiplication, but the subject is wrong in applying it.
- **[bottom picture]**: the subject has been multiplying completely and is able to apply the save technique in multiplication; but the subject does not understand the place value in multiplication

SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

$$16 \times 12 = 16 \times (2 + 10) = (16 \times 2) + (16 \times 10) = 32 + 160 = 192$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 16 \\ 12 \times \\ \hline 32 \\ 16 \quad + \\ \hline 192 \end{array}$$

Division

$$172 : 2 = 170$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 270 \\ 5 \overline{) 270} \\ \underline{220} \end{array}$$

$$\frac{28}{2} = 104$$

HOW?

- [top left picture]: $172 \div 2 = 172 - 2 = 170$
- [top right picture]

$$\begin{array}{r} 270 \\ 5 : \end{array} \Rightarrow \begin{array}{r} 270 \\ 5 - \\ \hline 220 \end{array}$$

- [bottom picture]: $2+2 = 4$ and $8+2 = 10$, then $28 \div 2 = 104$

WHY?

- the subject does not understand the concept of division as the inverse of multiplication and as repeated subtraction

SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

- teach the concept of division as the inverse of multiplication

$$10 \div 2 = 5 \text{ is equivalent to } 5 \times 2 = 10$$

- teach division as repeated subtraction

$10 \div 2 = 5$ is equivalent to subtracting 10 by 2 repeatedly 5 times until the remainder is 0.

$$\begin{array}{r} 1+1+1+1+1=5 \\ 2 \overline{) 10} \\ \underline{2} \quad - \\ 8 \\ \underline{2} \quad - \\ 6 \\ \underline{2} \quad - \\ 4 \\ \underline{2} \quad - \\ 2 \\ \underline{2} \quad - \\ 0 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 50+30+5+1=86 \\ 2 \overline{) 172} \\ \underline{100} \quad - \\ 72 \\ \underline{60} \quad - \\ 12 \\ \underline{10} \quad - \\ 2 \\ \underline{2} \quad - \\ 0 \end{array}$$

In general, the cause of errors is the limited knowledge of the prerequisites for performing arithmetic operations.

Nonetheless, some traces of student reasoning show noteworthy "creative thinking". Teachers can use this line of reasoning to improve students' reasoning processes..

CONCLUSION

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON DIGITAL EDUCATION
AND SOCIAL SCIENCE (2022) ICDESS 2022

